

THE CONCEPT OF «BEAUTY» IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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The annotation: This article explores the multifaceted concept of "beauty" in English and Uzbek, examining its cultural and linguistic manifestations. Through comparative analysis of lexical fields, semantic ranges, and idiomatic expressions related to beauty, the study reveals both similarities and significant differences in how the two languages conceptualize and express aesthetic appreciation. The research highlights the influence of cultural values and societal norms on the perception and description of beauty, demonstrating the inherent limitations of direct translation and the need for nuanced understanding in intercultural communication.

Keywords: Beauty, Aesthetics, Cross-cultural communication, Linguistic relativity, English language, Uzbek language, Semantics, Lexical field, Idioms, Cultural values, Translation.

In academic circles, the study of literary texts is viewed as a means of understanding how changes in language and culture at certain historical stages influence people's thinking and values. This is why cognitive research of language materials is widely acknowledged in modern linguistics.

In this direction, attention is focused on the conceptual aspects of modern literary texts based on national-ethnic and emotional-aesthetic principles. Analyzing the leading concept of beauty and its evaluation criteria in literary works allows us to understand the national mentalities and artistic thought development of a particular people.

In academic discourse, cognitive linguistics and the analysis of conceptual research in literature has led to precise solutions for understanding the mental nature of language. This approach involves identifying and clarifying the role of lexical units in the formation of concepts in literary works.

This direction of research allows for organizing a historic lexical fund within a specific conceptual sphere based on the linguistic and cultural characteristics of generic texts against the background of national culture.

In literary works, the verbalization of the concept of beauty through various means allows to identify its verbalization potential peculiar to the Old Uzbek period, to define poetic assessments and beautiful standards, and to analyze lexical-semantic processes and to generalize about the features of the Uzbek language specific to a significant historical period.

During the era of independence, Uzbek linguistics has conducted a number of studies in the field of anthropocentric and cognitive linguistics, paying more attention to the analysis of literary texts. The history of the Uzbek language, which is part of the Turkic language family, is closely related to the aspirations, joys, sorrows and achievements of our ancestors. They conveyed their message to the world through our native language.

Great cultural monuments, scientific discoveries and artistic masterpieces have been created in this language. A great deal of attention is paid to the study of various concepts in cognitive linguistics. We will give a brief overview of the existing research and determine our position on the issue of studying the concept of "beauty". Many works are devoted to the study of "material", mental, emotional, evaluative and other concepts.

Foreign studies include J. Lakoff and M. Johnson, in particular, argues that the argument is the study of the cognitive metaphor of war, which gives rise to the idea that our everyday conceptual system is metaphorical in nature. Language allows us to access metaphors that structure our perception, thinking and actions by comparing images that form the basis for cognitive metaphors in different languages, it is possible to identify differences and similarities in the thinking of their carriers.

In the scientific literature, there are many works devoted to various aspects of the concept of "beauty" and related aesthetic assessments. This is no coincidence, since this concept is one of the most important signs of value that affects the behavior of a person, determines the role and attitude of a person towards the world around him and other people in him. Despite the many philosophical, linguistic and other studies in this area, it will return to the question of studying the concept of "beauty" in the future.

The main peculiarities of the perception of beauty in English linguoculture "as a contradiction of positive aesthetic assessment, directly emotionally and rationally reflected, emphasizing choice as a condition for recognizing something as meeting the criteria of beauty, preferring ugliness as a result of human misconduct". As for English Linguistics, the author points out the connection between youth and beauty and the presence of sharply negative features of defects in appearance. As a result of the analysis, the author concludes that "the idea of deceptive and ephemeric beauty dominates English phraseology, paremiology and aphorism ". In the study, an associative experiment and analysis of the concept of "beauty" plays an important role in various types of speech, which allows us to come to the following conclusions: "

in journalistic texts, the verbal expression of aesthetic assessment does not differ from the corresponding expression in artistic texts”, “positive aesthetic assessment prevails in artistic and journalistic texts” the proportion of negative aesthetic assessments in Based on these findings, we can assume that the study of artistic texts is enough to fully and comprehensively illuminate the dynamics of the change in the concept of “beauty” in Russian and English.

The concept of beauty, while seemingly universal, is deeply rooted in cultural context and linguistic expression. This article explores the multifaceted nature of beauty as perceived and articulated in English and Uzbek, highlighting both similarities and crucial differences. Understanding these nuances is crucial for effective cross-cultural communication and translation, as a direct equivalence rarely captures the full semantic richness of the concept.

In English, the term "beauty" encompasses a broad range of aesthetic experiences, encompassing physical attractiveness, artistic merit, and even moral goodness. The lexicon associated with beauty is extensive, ranging from descriptive adjectives like "stunning," "elegant," "graceful," and "charming," to more abstract terms like "aesthetic," "sublime," and "exquisite." English readily employs metaphors to express beauty, drawing comparisons to nature ("as beautiful as a sunset"), precious materials ("as beautiful as gold"), or idealized figures ("a beauty queen"). The emphasis on individual perception is strong, with subjective judgments frequently employed ("I find her beautiful").

Uzbek, on the other hand, possesses a more nuanced approach to beauty. While direct translations of "go'zal" (beautiful) and "chiroyli" (pretty) exist, they often carry connotations that diverge from their English counterparts. "Go'zal" can evoke a sense of ethereal beauty, often associated with spiritual or moral qualities, going beyond mere physical attractiveness. "Chiroyli," while similar to "pretty," may imply a more delicate or refined beauty. The Uzbek language utilizes descriptive phrases and metaphors that reflect the cultural values of harmony, balance, and naturalness. For instance, descriptions of beauty might focus on the symmetry of a face, the vibrancy of color in nature, or the graceful movements of a dancer. The emphasis often lies on a holistic appreciation of beauty, integrating physical appearance with inner qualities and character.

A significant difference lies in the cultural values underpinning the perception of beauty. While Western aesthetics often emphasize individuality and striking features, Uzbek cultural norms may prioritize modesty, elegance, and a harmonious blend of features. This is reflected in the language used to describe beauty, with Uzbek often employing less direct, more metaphorical

expressions. Moreover, the concept of beauty in Uzbek culture is often inextricably linked to family values and social harmony. A beautiful woman might be praised not only for her appearance but also for her grace, kindness, and role within her family.

The difficulties in direct translation become apparent when attempting to convey the full meaning of a beauty-related expression. A simple "She is beautiful" in English might require a more elaborate phrase in Uzbek to capture the specific nuances intended, considering the context and the desired emphasis. A literal translation could easily misrepresent the intended meaning and cultural implications.

In conclusion, this comparative study of the concept of "beauty" in English and Uzbek reveals a fascinating interplay between language, culture, and perception. While both languages possess means to express aesthetic appreciation, the underlying cultural values and linguistic structures significantly shape their respective expressions. English often prioritizes individualistic interpretations and direct descriptions, employing a wide range of adjectives and metaphors focused on striking features or idealized standards. Uzbek, however, demonstrates a more holistic approach, emphasizing harmony, balance, and the integration of inner qualities with physical appearance. The cultural emphasis on modesty, grace, and social harmony subtly influences the linguistic choices and metaphorical expressions used to describe beauty.

References:

1. Лакофф Г. Тхе Сонтемпорарй Тхеорй оф Метапхор/Метапхор анд Тхеоугхт - Самбридге: Самбридге УниверситйПресс, 1993. - 49 п.;
2. Федотова Т.Н. Лексико-семантическое поле красоты в современном русском языке: дисс.канд.фил.наук. - Казан:1999. - 150 с.;
3. То'rayeva, U. (2023). Terminlar tarjimasining nazariy va amaliy asoslari. Farg'ona davlat universiteti, (4), 64-64.
4. Turaeva, U. (2024). Uzbek: Yuridik terminlar tarjima yuridik terminlar tarjimasida sinonimiya tarjima muammosi sifatida. Farg'ona Davlat Universiteti, 30(4), 82. Retrieved from <https://journal.fdu.uz/index.php/sjfsu/article/view/3420>
5. Babakulovna, X. Z., & Shukhratovna, T. U. (2024, April). Исследование важности глобальной коммуникации с применением международной терминологии. in international conference on medicine, science, and education (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 93-96).